

Boiling Water Reactor Group Constant Model for Nodal Neutronics Solver Ants

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ABSTRACT

The development of the nodal neutronics code Ants has been ongoing at VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd since 2017. Ants has been verified and validated for pressurized water reactors (PWRs) in steady-state, transient and burnup scenarios. So far, the applications have not included boiling water reactors (BWRs). The current group constant model in Ants is not ideal for modeling phenomena present in BWRs. The plutonium history approach for parametrizing history effects cannot account for the separate effects arising from the steep void profile and long-term control rod insertion of BWRs. Therefore, a new group constant model suitable for BWR modeling has been implemented. The new model applies the polynomial fitting of group constants, which before was conducted only for momentary feedback variables, to history parameters as well. That is, the history parameters for control rod history and coolant density history are included as separate feedback variables in the group constant model. The model was tested with the CBH benchmark scenario including a 2x2 core with subsequent rodged and unrodged depletion. The results of the new model were compared against the high-fidelity Serpent solution, and the improvement from existing plutonium history based group constant model was evaluated. Compared to the reference Serpent solution, the effective multiplication factor was not significantly improved from the solution using the plutonium history based group constant model. However, pin power estimates and axial power distributions showed better agreement with the new polynomial based history model.

Keywords: BWR, nodal neutronics, group constants, Ants, Serpent

1. INTRODUCTION

The nodal neutronics code Ants has been developed at VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd (VTT) since 2017 [1]. Ants serves as the reduced-order neutronics solver in the Kraken computational framework [2]. The Kraken framework couples neutronics, thermal hydraulics and fuel behavior codes for burnup, transient and fuel cycle simulations. The framework is built around the Monte Carlo transport code Serpent, which has been developed at VTT since 2004 [3]. By generating group constants for Ants with Serpent, Ants methodology can be verified thoroughly by comparing it against the full-scale high-fidelity Serpent solution. In depletion problems, Ants has been shown to be capable of modeling PWRs successfully [4, 5]. However, it was expected that the existing methodology for group constant parametrization is not applicable for modeling depletion in BWRs due to the separate effects caused by high void fractions and long-term control rod insertion.

The neutron spectrum in which the fuel is depleted affects the isotopic composition of the fuel. This can be seen in the atomic density of Pu-239, as a harder spectrum produces more Pu-239 than a softer spectrum. In BWRs, two separate history effects, void history effect and control rod history effect, are present and affect the plutonium density in different manners. The void history effect is radially even throughout the assembly, whereas the control rod history causes more local changes. Since the control rod in BWRs consists of blades inserted between assemblies, the control rod creates a harder spectrum

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in the peripheral fuel pins close to the blade due to increased absorption of thermal neutrons. In long-term insertion, the isotopic composition in the assembly is affected especially in the fuel pins closest to the blade. Due to the different local effects of the void and control rod histories, the two need to be separated in the evaluation of the group constants within the nodal code. This phenomenon has been tackled by many nodal codes, for instance the POLCA8 nodal core simulator [6]. However, review of existing methods is not in the scope of this paper.

This work includes implementing a method for parametrizing group constant history variables within the GenPoly group constant model used in Ants. The new methodology is tested with the control blade history (CBH) benchmark problem.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. GenPoly Group Constant Model

The Serpent-Ants calculation chain utilizes the GenPoly group constant format [7]. In GenPoly, the changes in group constants from nominal conditions due to feedback effects are modeled as polynomials. The polynomial of an arbitrary number of terms, in which the group constants are interpolated, can be chosen by the user in the processing phase of the group constants. The polynomial is fitted based on the evaluated state points using a least squares fitting algorithm. The group constant value Σ in local conditions (fb) at burnup (bu) is thus evaluated as

$$\Sigma_{fb}(bu) = \Sigma_{nom}(bu) + \mathcal{P}_{\Sigma}(fb,bu), \quad (1)$$

where $\Sigma_{nom}(bu)$ is the value of the group constant in nominal conditions at burnup (bu), and $\mathcal{P}_{\Sigma}(fb,bu)$ is the polynomial reflecting the change of the group constant due to change in feedback variables, evaluated in condition (fb) at burnup (bu). The polynomial can be chosen, for instance, as

$$\mathcal{P}_{\Sigma}(fb,bu) = c_1(bu)\Delta\rho_c + c_2(bu)(\Delta\rho_c)^2 + c_3(bu)\Delta\sqrt{T_f}, \quad (2)$$

where $\Delta\rho_c$ and $\Delta\sqrt{T_f}$ correspond to the change in coolant density and square root of fuel temperature between nominal condition (nom) and current local condition (fb). The fitting coefficients c_i are tabulated for each burnup point. In the equation, the feedback effect of the coolant density change is modeled as a second order dependence and the feedback effect of the fuel temperature change is modeled as a first order dependence of the square root of fuel temperature. In addition to the coolant density and fuel temperature, possible feedback variables for the polynomial include coolant temperature, boron concentration, etc., reflecting the momentary changes present in the core. All macroscopic cross sections, diffusion coefficients and discontinuity factors are parametrized with the same polynomial interpolation.

The current way of modeling history effects in the GenPoly group constant model is based on a plutonium history approach. The atomic density of Pu-239 is tracked in Ants at node level and is used to interpolate the group constants of the node between nominal and off-nominal history conditions. That is, a change from the nominal plutonium atomic density results in emphasizing more towards the group constants calculated with off-nominal history. The plutonium history approach is suitable for PWR applications [8]. However, the method does not separate the source of the change in the plutonium density. Therefore, a separate methodology is needed to model the separate local effects of void history and control rod history, which are present in BWRs.

Figure 1. The evolution of thermal absorption cross section based on different depletion histories (left). The black lines represent different scenarios, in which control rod is inserted at different stages of depletion. All cases have been restarted without the presence of control rod in all burnup points to visualize only the history effect. The right figure illustrates the same scenarios normalized between the rodded and unrodded histories visualizing the realistic evolution of the interpolation value w_{HCR} .

2.2. Polynomial BWR History Parametrization

The effects of the void and control rod histories can be separated utilizing historical variables $\rho_{c,H}$ and w_{HCR} , representing the coolant density (void) history and control rod history, respectively. During depletion in nodal calculations, the variables are accumulated at the node level based on the prevailing conditions at each burnup point. The coolant density history $\rho_{c,H}$ essentially represents the constant momentary coolant density state, in which the node could be depleted to obtain the same historical state resulting from changing void conditions. The control rod history variable w_{HCR} represents the interpolation value of a group constant between unrodded history and rodded history. A physical interpretation of the interpolation value is illustrated in Fig. 1. The calculations for obtaining these figures were conducted with Serpent in an infinite lattice model. The figure on the left shows the evolution of thermal absorption cross section in different scenarios. The right figure shows the interpolation value between rodded and unrodded histories for thermal absorption cross section for the same scenarios. The statistical variations in the Serpent calculations are emphasized at low burnups, where the difference between rodded and unrodded history is very small, as seen at low burnups in the right-hand-side of Fig 1. The control rod history variable w_{HCR} can be modeled in Ants imitating the black curves of the right-hand-side of Fig. 1. However, the actual interpolation value, given here only for thermal absorption cross section, might behave differently for different group constants. In this work, all group constants are modeled with the same w_{HCR} dependence for simplicity. Matching the accumulation of w_{HCR} accurately for the interpolation value of one group constant might not result in the best possible fit for the other group constants.

So far, Ants has not utilized history variables in the parametrization, as the history effects have been accounted for with the plutonium history method. In order to model the effects of the two history variables separately, the variables were added to the GenPoly model as new feedback variables. The accumulation of the history variables was conducted as simple averages. That is, for instance for the control rod history variable, the value is updated on each burnup step as the node burnup accumulated in rodded state divided by the total burnup of the node. This is not an accurate representation of the interpolation value, however, it will suffice for the early testing of the model. The evaluation of the history variables was still conducted outside Ants for these test calculations.

The dependence of the history variables on the group constants was implemented by adding the history variables into the feedback polynomial as separate feedback variables. That is, the history branches calculated with Serpent were not processed as historical states that determine the nominal and off-nominal states for the plutonium history approach, but rather as separate branches for the polynomial fitting. The full polynomial of the history and feedback effects is presented in the next section with the specification of the test case.

2.3. Description of Test Case: CBH Benchmark

The control blade history (CBH) benchmark is a stand-alone neutronics benchmark by Studsvik Scandpower [9]. The aim of the benchmark is to test the capabilities of nodal codes to evaluate pin power distributions in a BWR scenario with long-term control rod insertion and a steep axial void profile. The control blade history effect refers to the power peaking occurring in the fuel rods near-by a recently withdrawn control blade.

The benchmark model consists of a 2x2 assembly mini-core with reflective radial boundary conditions. Axially, the assemblies are full height BWR assemblies including partial-length fuel rods (PLFRs) and a realistic axial void profile. Axial reflectors consisting of unvoided coolant are included in the top and bottom of the assemblies. The geometry of the model is shown in Fig. 2. The calculation scheme consists of a depletion of the system up to 10 MWd/kgU with a partially inserted control rod in one of the assemblies until 5.0 MWd/kgU. The axial coolant density profile remains constant throughout the depletion.

The group constants were calculated with Serpent for all axial levels of the assembly. A total of 8 history branches were calculated, consisting of 4 void conditions with and without the presence of control rod. Similar 8 momentary branches were calculated for each history. The parameters of the group constant generation calculation are shown in Tab. I. The step sizes in the burnup calculations varied between 0.001 and 0.5 MWd/kgU and in the branch calculations between 0.001 and 1.0 MWd/kgU.

Figure 2. The radial and axial geometries of the CBH benchmark model. The top left corner shows the control blade, which is half-way inserted from the bottom.

Table I. The calculation matrix for the fuel homogenization in the CBH benchmark.

State parameter	Unit	Number of values	Range of values
Unrodded depletion burnup steps	MWd/kgU	64	0.0 – 20.0
Rodded depletion burnup steps	MWd/kgU	64	0.0 – 20.0
Branch burnup steps	MWd/kgU	24	0.0 – 20.0
Coolant void histories	%	4	00, 30, 60, 90
Coolant void branches	%	4	00, 30, 60, 90
Void branches with CR insertion	%	4	00, 30, 60, 90
Void branches with CR withdrawal	%	4	00, 30, 60, 90

The polynomial reflecting the feedback effects (and in this case, also historical effects) was chosen based on the evaluated state points as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{P}_{\Sigma}(\text{fb}) = & c_1 \Delta\rho_c + c_2 (\Delta\rho_c)^2 + c_3 (\Delta\rho_c)^3 \\
 & + c_4 \Delta\rho_{c,H} + c_5 (\Delta\rho_{c,H})^2 + c_6 (\Delta\rho_{c,H})^3 \\
 & + c_7 \Delta w_{\text{HCR}} \\
 & + c_8 (\Delta w_{\text{HCR}}) (\Delta\rho_c) + c_9 (\Delta w_{\text{HCR}}) (\Delta\rho_c)^2 + c_{10} (\Delta w_{\text{HCR}}) (\Delta\rho_c)^3 \\
 & + c_{11} (\Delta w_{\text{HCR}}) (\Delta\rho_{c,H}) + c_{12} (\Delta w_{\text{HCR}}) (\Delta\rho_{c,H})^2 + c_{13} (\Delta w_{\text{HCR}}) (\Delta\rho_{c,H})^3 \\
 & + c_{14} (\Delta\rho_c) (\Delta\rho_{c,H}) + c_{15} (\Delta\rho_c) (\Delta\rho_{c,H})^2 + c_{16} (\Delta\rho_c) (\Delta\rho_{c,H})^3 \\
 & + c_{17} (\Delta\rho_c)^2 (\Delta\rho_{c,H}) + c_{18} (\Delta\rho_c)^2 (\Delta\rho_{c,H})^2 + c_{19} (\Delta\rho_c)^2 (\Delta\rho_{c,H})^3 \\
 & + c_{20} (\Delta\rho_c)^3 (\Delta\rho_{c,H}) + c_{21} (\Delta\rho_c)^3 (\Delta\rho_{c,H})^2 + c_{22} (\Delta\rho_c)^3 (\Delta\rho_{c,H})^3 \\
 & + c_{23} (\Delta w_{\text{HCR}}) (\Delta\rho_c) (\Delta\rho_{c,H}) + c_{24} (\Delta w_{\text{HCR}}) (\Delta\rho_c) (\Delta\rho_{c,H})^2 + c_{25} (\Delta w_{\text{HCR}}) (\Delta\rho_c) (\Delta\rho_{c,H})^3 \\
 & + c_{26} (\Delta w_{\text{HCR}}) (\Delta\rho_c)^2 (\Delta\rho_{c,H}) + c_{27} (\Delta w_{\text{HCR}}) (\Delta\rho_c)^2 (\Delta\rho_{c,H})^2 + c_{28} (\Delta w_{\text{HCR}}) (\Delta\rho_c)^2 (\Delta\rho_{c,H})^3 \\
 & + c_{29} (\Delta w_{\text{HCR}}) (\Delta\rho_c)^3 (\Delta\rho_{c,H}) + c_{30} (\Delta w_{\text{HCR}}) (\Delta\rho_c)^3 (\Delta\rho_{c,H})^2 + c_{31} (\Delta w_{\text{HCR}}) (\Delta\rho_c)^3 (\Delta\rho_{c,H})^3.
 \end{aligned}$$

The polynomial includes third degree terms for coolant density ρ_c and coolant density history $\rho_{c,H}$, and a first order term for control rod history w_{HCR} . In addition, cross terms between all of these terms are included. The 31 terms together with the constant term reflecting the nominal state, form the full polynomial of the 32 calculated state points (8 histories x 4 momentary coolant states). The momentary control rod presence is modeled as a separate material, with Ants handling the use of rodded or unrodded group constants automatically. Including all cross terms in the polynomial might be excessive, and evaluating the relevance of the terms is needed. However, for early testing of the model, all cross terms were included in order to avoid neglecting part of the information obtained from the state point calculations.

3. RESULTS

The Ants results of the CBH benchmark with two energy groups using the new polynomial history parametrization are compared to the high-fidelity Serpent solution. In addition, an Ants solution utilizing the plutonium history method for group constant history parametrization is included to demonstrate the effect of the new parametrization. With the plutonium history parametrization, only two burnup histories, nominal and off-nominal, can be used for the group constants. Here, unrodded state with void fraction of 30 % was chosen for nominal history and rodded state with 60 % void was chosen for off-nominal history. In this scenario with 8 calculated history state points, the nominal and off-nominal histories could be chosen in many ways for the plutonium history parametrization.

Figure 3. Effective multiplication factor as a function of burnup. The unfilled markers correspond to the reactivity difference from the Serpent reference solution.

The Ants burnup calculation was calculated with a step size of 0.25 MWd/kgU until 10 MWd/kgU. An additional step was added at burnup 4.999 MWd/kgU after which the half-way inserted control rod is withdrawn at 5.0 MWd/kgU. The effective multiplication factor (k_{eff}) of the system is shown in Fig. 3. The figure includes Ants solutions for the new polynomial history parametrization and the plutonium history based parametrization as well as the reference Serpent solution. The difference in reactivity against Serpent for both Ants solutions is shown as unfilled markers. Both Ants solutions reach a maximum difference of +380 pcm. In low burnups, the plutonium history method has slightly better agreement with Serpent compared to the polynomial history method. A larger difference occurs at higher burnups, where the polynomial history method results in approximately 200 pcm better agreement compared to the plutonium history method.

The axial power distributions before and after the withdrawal of the control rod are shown in Fig. 4. The power is peaked in the bottom of the core due to the axial void profile. The absolute difference in axial power between the Ants solution and the reference Serpent solution is improved with the new model. The maximum differences with the plutonium history model for the two burnup steps are 21 % and 18 %, whereas for the polynomial history model, the respective differences are 7.4 % and 3.6 %.

Figure 4. Normalized axial power distribution before withdrawal of control rod and after withdrawal of control rod. The unfilled markers indicate the absolute difference from the reference Serpent solution.

Figure 5. Maximum differences and RMS deviations of assembly power (left) and pin power (right) distributions as a function of burnup.

The assembly and pin power peaking maximum and RMS differences are shown as a function of burnup in Fig. 5 for the plutonium history method and the polynomial history method. In the beginning of the calculation, the two methods show nearly identical behavior in the power distributions, as the history effects are still negligible. At zero burnup and during the rodded phase, the maximum pin peaking differences range between 9 % and 17 % for both methods. In this phase of depletion, the maximum differences occur at the pins near the control blade, in which the powers are low. The low-power pins are emphasized in the relative differences. At the withdrawal of the control rod at 5.0 MWd/kgU, the maximum differences of the polynomial history method for both assembly and pin level powers drop.

The difference between the two methods is especially noticeable in the maximum pin power difference at 5.0 MWd/kgU when the control rod is withdrawn. At this point, the CBH effect is at its highest. The Ants pin powers calculated with the polynomial history method have maximum difference of 4.5 %, whereas using the plutonium history method results in a maximum pin power difference of 43 %. The RMS difference is also improved with the polynomial history method from 1.8 % to 0.8 %. However, between 8 and 10 MWd/kgU, the plutonium history parametrization results in a better agreement with Serpent compared to the polynomial history method, at both assembly and pin level.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The development and applications of the nodal neutronics solver Ants have in the past focused on modeling PWRs. The existing GenPoly group constant model uses a plutonium history method for parametrizing the group constants. In the plutonium history method, the group constants are weighted between nominal and off-nominal histories based on the Pu-239 density. For BWR applications, in which high void fractions and long-term control rod insertions are present, a new group constant history parametrization model was implemented. In the new history parametrization, the history parameters are treated directly as feedback variables. The dependence of the variables on the group constants is modeled as a polynomial fitted to the evaluated state points. This allows including multiple history state points in the group constants.

The new polynomial history method was tested with the CBH benchmark. The benchmark scenario was modeled with Ants using both the existing plutonium history method and the new polynomial history method. The reference solution was calculated with Serpent. In general, the new polynomial history method improves the Ants solution in contrast to the plutonium history method in this BWR

application. The axial and radial power distributions show good agreement with the Serpent results. However, the differences in the effective multiplication factor are still surprisingly large throughout the depletion.

The plutonium history reference was calculated with one selection of nominal and off-nominal histories for the group constants. The histories can be chosen in many ways and results are affected based on the selection [10].

At higher burnups, the differences in radial and axial powers using the polynomial history method become larger. This could be explained with the way the history parameters are accumulated. For this test, the control rod history parameter w_{HCR} was accumulated by calculating the fraction of node burnup accumulated in the rodded state at each burnup step. Refining the evaluation of the control rod history parameter might effect the results especially at high burnups. The accumulation of the coolant density history parameter does not affect the results in this scenario, as the coolant density profile is constant throughout the calculation. Setting the history parameter values and their accumulation is still conducted by the user. Future work includes implementing this process into Ants as well as tackling the other effects aside from control rod and void history effects.

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